

EVALUATION OF EPOXY/FLAX-FIBRE SANDWICH PANELS AS AN ALTERNATIVE TO BIRCH PLYWOOD ON CARGO BICYCLES

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Epoxy/flax-fibre sandwich panels were shown to be a suitable alternative to birch plywood for the carrying box of a cargo bicycle. Weight savings can be realized by implementing a monocoque design where a natural fibre composite carrying box functions as a structural component of the cargo bicycle. A UV resistant clear acrylic surface coating applied to the sandwich panel proved to be effective at preventing colour change from UV light exposure in comparison to a black phenolic film used on the birch plywood. This allows for epoxy/flax-fibre substrates to be protected from weathering while still maintaining their natural aesthetic.

INTRODUCTION

Cargo bicycles are a popular alternative to cars for transporting cargo and people in busy metropolitan areas. A defining feature of the cargo bicycle is the carrying box or compartment that is integrated into the structure of the bicycle frame. Usually this box is situated in front of the rider and is supported on each side by a wheel, whereas the rear portion of the bicycle frame is the same as a regular bicycle. The box is typically large enough to carry 0.5 m³ of cargo, or one to two adult passengers. On a traditional cargo bicycle the carrying box is made from plywood fastened together and is supported by an aluminium or steel space-frame construction. This design has its limitations however, because it is not practical to create curved surfaces from flat sheets of plywood which would allow for more aerodynamic or aesthetically pleasing forms to be fabricated. This type of construction also tends to be quite heavy because the plywood must be thick enough to withstand the forces and bending moments imposed on it by the cargo and passengers. Fasteners and brackets are also required to hold the sides of the box together, as well as to connect it to the space-frame construction. This also adds weight to the cargo bicycle.

Natural fibre composites (NFCs) are increasingly being used in semi-structural applications because they offer low density, high stiffness, good damping and low environmental impact. The specific stiffness for a unidirectional (UD) cellulose fibre composite for example can be higher than that of a UD glass fibre laminate at the same fibre volume fraction [1]. NFCs also require less energy to produce than synthetic fibres such as carbon-fibre which has ~75 times the embodied energy of flax-fibre [2]. Continuously reinforced NFCs are also aesthetically pleasing when manufactured with a translucent matrix, as the fibres give the laminate an organic appearance and a natural earth tone colour. This is important for products that wish to be marketed as being sustainable as this can be visually recognized by the consumer. There are some challenges though which limit the widespread use of NFCs. Natural fibres are hydrophilic and sensitive to moisture absorption, which means that water absorbed through the matrix into the natural fibres can lead to dimensional instabilities and microbial growth [2]. By applying a suitable surface treatment to the fibres, the amount of water absorption into the fibres can be reduced. Pinto et al. [3] showed that jute fibres with a silane surface treatment in an epoxy matrix increased the water resistance by 60%.

Using composites for the construction of a cargo bicycle carrying box appears to be a logical choice. This would allow for the individual panels of the box to be manufactured as a single piece, thereby eliminating the need for bolts and brackets. The box could also be designed to function as a structural part of the bicycle frame (i.e. monocoque), thus removing the need for a supporting space-frame structure. Furthermore, core material could be used to create sandwich panels in those regions of the box that require a higher bending stiffness. If NFCs were used, then this design could be made lighter and stiffer than a traditional cargo bicycle made from plywood. The total carbon footprint for the cargo bicycle would also most likely be less because the total mass of aluminium and steel used in the bicycle would be reduced. In addition to challenges with water absorption and microbial attack, NFCs with a transparent surface coating are prone to fading when exposed to UV light. A consumer product that changes in colour, particularly non-uniformly, is usually not desirable from an aesthetic perspective, so it is important to select a UV resistant surface coating that will minimize this effect.

This study evaluates the use of epoxy/flax-fibre sandwich panels with a clear acrylic, UV-resistant coating as a replacement to birch plywood as the panel material on cargo bicycles. This is achieved by first ensuring that the mechanical properties of an epoxy/flax-fibre sandwich panel are adequate for replacing plywood, and secondly by subjecting test specimens to accelerated weathering in order to measure changes in colour, gloss, warping, delamination and microorganism growth. Birch plywood with black phenolic film coating supplied by a local cargo bicycle manufacture, serves as the reference material for this study. Two acrylic surface coatings from different manufactures are tested in order to find a coating which works best on an epoxy substrate. The specimens will be exposed to continuous cycles of UV light and water spray for a total duration of 1,200 hours. Colour and gloss measurements will be made at 200 hour intervals, while changes in warping, delamination and microorganism growth will be conducted at the end of the test duration. Trend lines for the recorded data will be determined for the colour and gloss change of each test series, thereby providing a quantitative comparison between the reference material and the two acrylic coatings.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Birch plywood with phenolic film coating

Birch plywood made from 7 layers stacked orthogonally $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/\overline{90^\circ}]_s$ with black phenolic film coating was procured from a local cargo bike manufacture. The material thickness was 9.1mm and the area weight was 6.4 kg/m^3 . This material served as the reference for the accelerated weather testing.

Sandwich panel materials

SuperSap CLR epoxy resin system with CLX and INH hardener mixed with mass ratios of 19.3 : 19.3 : 100 hardener to resin was used as the matrix material. This resin system was supplied by Entropy Resin Systems Europe. For reinforcement, Biotex biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$ flax fabric with an areal weight of 600 g/m^2 was procured from Composites Evolution in Derbyshire, UK. The core material selected was ArmaFORM PET GR115, closed cell 100% recycled PET foam with a density of 115 kg/m^3 and was purchased from Armacell International. The core material thickness was 7 mm, and there were perforation holes (through holes) and orthogonal flow channels on one side to aid with resin infusion.

Surface coatings

Two types of clear lacquer were tested on the sandwich panels. NEXA Autocolor P190-6659 with P210-8815 hardener, two component acrylic thermoset system mixed with mass ratios of 1 : 3 activator to resin, supplied by Scandinavian Paint Solutions, and Cromax CC6400 with low emission

standard activator XK205, two component acrylic thermoset system mixed with mass ratios of 1 : 3 activator to resin, supplied by Lak Gruppen, DK.

Specimen fabrication

Sandwich panel specimens

A sandwich panel was produced by standard vacuum infusion procedure. The first step was to apply a mould release agent to the glass plate which served as the form for the panel. Two layers of biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$ flax fabric measuring 400mm x 600mm were then cut from the fabric roll, and one layer of core material was cut to the same dimensions. The flax fabric was dried for 1 hour at 80°C before processing. The flax fabric and core material (flow channels facing down), were then placed on the glass plate such that a symmetric sandwich panel layup was created. Peel ply and distribution media were placed over the dry laminate stack, and spiral tubes placed on either side. Tacky-tape was laid around the perimeter of the glass plate, and vacuum foil was placed over top of the distribution media and sealed to the glass plate by means of the tacky-tape. Vacuum hoses were connected to each of the spiral tubes. One vacuum hose (suction) was connected to a resin overflow chamber installed with a vacuum pressure gauge and regulator, while the other hose (inlet) was clamped closed. A vacuum pump was connected to the overflow chamber by means of an additional vacuum hose. The vacuum pump was started and the pressure reduced to a maximum value of 8 kPa (absolute). A leak test was performed and an acceptable drop in pressure recorded. The epoxy resin was then blended together and degassed under vacuum in order to remove entrained air bubbles. The vacuum hose was then placed inside the bucket and resin, and the valve from the vacuum pump to the overflow chamber re-opened. The regulator on the chamber was adjusted until a pressure of 60 kPa (absolute) was achieved. The clamp was then removed from the inlet vacuum hose and resin introduced into the dry laminate stack. Once the resin had saturated the stack and reached the suction side spiral hose, the inlet vacuum hose was clamped. The vacuum pressure was maintained at 60 kPa (absolute) by the vacuum pump for 16 hours. The sandwich panel was then demoulded and post-cured for 2 hours at 80°C.

Surface treatment

Six specimens 68 mm x 140 mm were cut from the sandwich panel. The faces of each specimen were prepared by sanding with a general purpose Scotch-Brite pad. Nexa Autocolor P190-6659 lacquer was then mixed with P210-8815 hardener at the appropriate mass ratio, and applied to the sides and faces of three of the specimens using a paint brush. The specimens were left to cure for 24 hours, and then a second layer of lacquer was applied to the faces of the specimens. The exposed sides of the birch plywood specimens were also sealed using Nexa Autocolor lacquer. The Cromax CC6400 lacquer with XK205 activator was mixed and applied to the remaining three sandwich panel specimens in similar manner.

Accelerated weather testing

Test series

A total of three test series for accelerated weathering were established based on the reference material and the sandwich panels with the two different surface coatings. An overview of these test series is presented in

Table 1. Each test series contains a reference specimen that was used to determine the amount of colour and gloss change.

A scratch completely penetrating the surface coating was made on one specimen from each test series using an abrasive circular saw. The purpose of the scratch was to provide an indication of whether exposed fibres and core material would greatly accelerate the deterioration of the sandwich panel in an outdoor environment.

	Specimen	Surface Coating	Description
Birch Plywood Panel	CB-00	Phenolic Film	Reference
	CB-01	Phenolic Film	-
	CB-02	Phenolic Film	With Surface Scratch
Epoxy/Flax-fibre Sandwich Panel	15-003-01	P190-6660	Reference
	15-003-02	P190-6660	-
	15-003-03	P190-6660	With Surface Scratch
	15-003-04	CC6400	Reference
	15-003-05	CC6400	-
	15-003-06	CC6400	With Surface Scratch

Table 1: Description of accelerated weather test specimens.

Test parameters

The test machine is designed so that one side of the panel always directly faces the UV light source. The accelerated weathering was conducted in accordance with ISO 4892-2, Plastics – Methods of exposure to laboratory light sources, Method A – Exposure using daylight filters (artificial weathering). A summary of the parameters used for the test are listed in Table 2 :

Parameter	Setting	Duty Cycle
UV Light Spectrum	Broadband 300-400 nm, Narrowband 340 nm	102 min
Deionized Water Spray	Sprayed On Front Of Specimens	18 min
Chamber Temperature	38°C	Continuous
Relative Humidity	50%	Continuous

Table 2: Accelerated weathering parameters.

The total exposure time for the plywood and sandwich panel specimens was 1,200 h.

Changes in colour and gloss

Changes in colour and gloss were measured every 200 h according to ISO 4582:2007(E), Plastics – Determination of changes in colour and variations in properties after exposure to daylight under glass, natural weathering or laboratory light sources. These measurements were performed using a Color-guide Sphere d/8° Spin hand held apparatus manufactured by BYK Gardner. The total change in colour (ΔE) was calculated based on the change of the individual colorimetric components (ΔL , Δa and Δb) relative to the reference specimen. Three measurements were taken on different locations on each panel, and the statistical mean and standard deviation was calculated. A $\Delta E = 1$ is generally equivalent to a change in colour which is barely perceivable to the naked eye.

Changes in gloss were measured according to EN ISO 2813, Paints and varnishes – Determination of specular gloss of non-metallic paint films at 20°, 60° and 85°. These measurements were performed using a micro-TR1-gloss hand held apparatus manufactured by BYK Gardner. Three measurements in different locations were made on each panel.

Warping, delamination and microorganism growth

At the end of the total test time, the first three test series were examined for warping, delamination and growth of microorganisms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Confirmation of material selection

Flax fibre was chosen because it is one of the best natural fibres for structural reinforcement and has a stiffness range of 50-90 GPa [1]. When these fibres are combined into yarns and used as continuous reinforcement, a UD laminate can be produced by means of vacuum infusion with a Young's modulus (E_1) of ~20 GPa [2]. Birch wood typically has a Young's modulus of 16 GPa [4] when measured in the grain direction. Therefore when combined with a suitable core material, it is possible to produce an epoxy/flax-fibre sandwich panel that has a higher specific bending stiffness than birch plywood.

Fabrication process

The epoxy/flax-fibre sandwich panel was measured to be 9.3mm thick with an area weight of 5.0 kg/m³ before the application of the surface coat. The thickness was slightly greater than the birch plywood reference material, however the area weight was 22% less.

The thickness of the surface coating for the P190-6659 lacquer varied moderately on each specimen. This unevenness may have occurred because of an incompatibility between the epoxy/flax-fibre substrate and the lacquer, or because the application method (paint brush) caused a non-uniform distribution of lacquer over the surface of the specimens. The surface coating for the CC6400 lacquer appeared to be incompatible with the substrate and resulted in small circular 'dry spots' where there was no surface coating at all on all of the specimens. This result was considered unsatisfactory and indicated that a primer layer should be considered in future trials. Despite this result, it was decided to test these specimens and to measure changes in colour and gloss on the regions that were sufficiently coated. The areas without surface coating would also provide an indication of how an unprotected epoxy/flax-fibre laminate would deteriorate when exposed for prolonged periods to UV light and water.

Changes in colour

Birch plywood panels with phenolic film coating

The birch plywood panels with phenolic film coating after accelerated weathering are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Birch plywood panels with phenolic film coating after 1,200 hours of accelerated weathering.

The specimen on the left is the reference and has not been subjected to accelerated weathering. The two specimens that have been tested clearly show a substantial change in colour that is uniform over the surface of the panel. A dark border can also be seen around the edges of the two specimens where they have been obscured by the frame of the fixture. The results for the colour change measurements for these two specimens are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Change in colour (ΔE) of birch plywood panels with phenolic film coating.

The change in colour (ΔE) was quite similar for both panels with specimen CB-02 reaching a maximum value of 18.9 ± 0.3 . The change in colour data appears to be following a power law relationship that will asymptotically approach a steady state value.

Sandwich panel with Nexa Autocolor surface coating

The sandwich panels with Nexa Autocolor P190-8815 surface coating after accelerated weathering are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Epoxy/Flax-fibre sandwich panels with Nexa Autocolor surface coating after 1,200 hours of accelerated weathering.

The two specimens on the right show a moderate change in colour compared to the reference. The colour change appears to be most significant on the flax fibres, thereby creating a grain like appearance. The results for the colour change measurements for these two specimens are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Change in colour (ΔE) of epoxy/flax-fibre sandwich panels with Nexa Autocolor P190-6659 surface coating.

The change in colour (ΔE) for the two specimens was quite consistent with respect to each other with specimens 15-003-02 reaching a maximum value of 8.9 ± 0.6 . The colour change data also appears to be following a power law function similar to the reference material.

Sandwich panel with Cromax CC6400 surface coating

The sandwich panels with Cromax CC6400 surface coating after accelerated weather testing are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Epoxy/Flax-fibre sandwich panels with Cromax CC6400 surface coating after 1,200 hours of accelerated weather testing.

As with the Nexa Autocolor test specimens, the two specimens that have been weather tested clearly show a moderate change in colour compared to the reference. Furthermore, a speckle pattern has emerged in the laminate at the locations where there are holes in the surface coating. In these locations exposed fibre bundles can be seen breaking through the surface of the matrix and are the

reason for the light colour. This is an indication of how a sandwich panel without protective surface coating would be damaged after prolonged exposure to an outdoor environment. The results for the colour change measurements for these two specimens are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Change in colour (ΔE) of epoxy/flax-fibre sandwich panels with Cromax CC6400 surface coating.

The change in colour (ΔE) for the two specimens deviated significantly from each other after 1,000 h of testing. One explanation for this is that the surface coating on specimen 15-003-05 is thicker than that on specimen 15-003-06, and therefore provides better UV protection. After 1,200 hours of exposure, the change in colour for specimens 15-003-05 and 15-003-06 were 12.3 ± 1.1 and 8.7 ± 0.8 respectively. The standard deviations for these measurements were notably higher than on the Nexa Autocolor specimens. This was also most likely attributed to variations in surface coating thickness.

Surface coating comparison

It was assumed that a power law function would best describe the relationship between ΔE and Time for the reference material and sandwich panel test series. The colour change test data for each test series (i.e. two specimens) were pooled together and a linear fit of a log-log plot used to determine the constants of a power law function. Each power law function was then plotted over the total test duration in order to develop trend lines that would allow for a comparison between each test series. The results from this analysis are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Comparison of change in colour for the phenolic film (reference) series in relation to the acrylic coated test series.

The two types of acrylic coating appear to perform equally well with the P190-6659 coating providing slightly better UV protection for exposure times greater than 600 hours. The change in colour of the birch plywood with phenolic film coating was almost twice as much as the test series with acrylic coatings at the end of the exposure duration. All test series had a $\Delta E > 1$ after 200 hours of exposure, indicating that a colour change perceivable by the naked eye had occurred during the first interval of exposure.

Changes in gloss

The gloss retention measurements taken on the two acrylic coated test series showed large scatter. This was most likely due to the unevenness of the surface coating. It was therefore decided to discontinue these measurements after the first 200 hour interval. Based on these observations, the surface coating application will be modified in future studies by spraying the surface coating on to the substrate.

Warping, delamination and microorganism growth

No visible warping or delamination were noted on the reference or sandwich panel test series after 1,200 hours of exposure. There was however, some minor de-bonding between the fibres and matrix around the surface scratch regions. This damage occurred, partially at least, during the manufacturing of the surface scratches and it does not appear that significant additional de-bonding has occurred due to water ingress. No growth of microorganisms were detected on any of the three test series.

CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluated the use of epoxy/flax-fibre sandwich panels with acrylic UV resistant coating as an alternative to birch plywood on cargo bicycles. This was achieved by first ensuring the material selection from a mechanical properties perspective, and then by evaluating the effects of accelerated weathering. Based on this approach, the following conclusions can be drawn from this study:

- Epoxy/flax-fibre sandwich panels can be manufactured with a higher specific bending stiffness than birch plywood by means of standard vacuum infusion.
- The birch plywood with black phenolic coating showed almost twice as much change in colour ($\Delta E = \sim 19$) compared to the acrylic coated sandwich panels after 1,200 hours of accelerated weathering.
- The Auto Nexacolor P190-6659 and Cromax CC6400 were nearly equal in performance regarding their ability to protect an epoxy/flax-fibre laminate from UV light and water spray, with the Auto Nexacolor P190-6659 showing slightly better protection for exposure periods greater than 400 hours.
- The Cromax CC6400 was especially difficult to apply evenly to the sandwich panel specimens, and resulted in 'holes' in the surface coating. These locations developed damage in the matrix and exposed fibres during the accelerated weathering.
- All of the laminates tested showed perceivable changes in colour within the first 200 hours of accelerated weather testing.

FUTURE WORK

Static tensile tests will be performed on epoxy/flax-fibre laminate specimens that have undergone accelerated weathering. The strength and stiffness results will be compared to reference specimens and knock-down factors (partial coefficients) determined for these material properties.

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